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ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Conservator/Restorer Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Monitor Condition

Data collected in Real Time

Challenges in Monitoring Conditions

Conservator/Restorer Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

Conservator/Restorer Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

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Conservator/Restorer Cross-analysis insights

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TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	Photographic or high-resolution images	3D scans	Environmental monitoring data (temperature, humidity, pollutants, etc.)	Chemical or physical analyses	Historical documentation	Structural monitoring data	Advanced scientific imaging data (radiography, thermography, multispectral)	Stratigraphic data (paint stratigraphy, material layers)	Spectroscopic data (FTIR, Raman, XRF, etc.)	Audio and video materials
High-resolution digital photography	23	13	17	15	22	7	9	11	13	7
Multispectral imaging (UV, IR, X-ray, etc.)	18	11	16	14	16	6	9	9	12	7
3D modelling	11	9	8	8	11	5	5	7	6	4
Software for restoration documentation	10	8	9	7	10	5	5	6	6	3
Spectroscopic tools (XRF, Raman, FTIR, etc.)	13	8	11	11	12	4	8	7	11	7
Radiography and tomography (X-ray, CT scan)	7	6	5	7	5	2	6	4	7	3
Infrared thermography	6	6	4	4	6	4	4	4	4	2
Digital microscopy	16	10	12	12	16	4	8	8	11	6
I don't use digital tools	1	1	0	0	2	1	1	0	0	1

TECHNOLOGIES × REAL-TIME DATA	Yes, continuously collected and updated (e.g., environmental sensors)	Yes, but only in specific situations or at scheduled intervals	No, data collection occurs manually or only as needed	I'm not sure / Not applicable	MONITORING TOOLS × MONITORING CHALLENGES	Difficulty obtaining accurate and reliable data	Lack of adequate technological tools	High cost of tools, systems, or software	Complexity in interpreting data	Difficulty in maintaining digital tools	Integration difficulties between traditional and digital practices	I don't experience particular difficulties
High-resolution digital photography	5	11	7	0	Environmental sensors (e.g., humidity, temperature, pollutants)	4	3	17	6	8	5	5
Multispectral imaging (UV, IR, X-ray, etc.)	2	12	4	0	Multispectral or hyperspectral imaging systems	2	0	5	3	3	2	1
3D modelling	3	5	4	0	Crack monitors or structural monitoring devices	3	0	4	2	1	0	1
Software for restoration documentation	4	5	1	0	Continuous condition monitoring systems	2	2	5	3	1	1	1
Spectroscopic tools (XRF, Raman, FTIR, etc.)	2	9	2	0	Data loggers or automated recording devices	3	2	12	4	7	3	3
Radiography and tomography (X-ray, CT scan)	1	6	0	0	I do not use digital tools for monitoring	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
Infrared thermography	2	4	1	0								
Digital microscopy	1	11	5	0								
I don't use digital tools	0	1	1	1								

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	Unstructured files (PDF, Word, etc.)	Relational databases	Scientific image formats (TIFF, RAW, DICOM, etc.)	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds)	Proprietary software formats	Tabular datasets (CSV, Excel, etc.)
Photographic or high-resolution images	20	6	13	9	7	13
3D scans	11	3	10	8	3	7
Environmental monitoring data (temperature, humidity, pollutants, etc.)	15	5	11	7	7	12
Chemical or physical analyses	14	3	10	7	4	11
Historical documentation	20	5	12	9	7	13
Structural monitoring data	6	3	3	3	3	3
Advanced scientific imaging data (radiography, thermography, multispectral)	7	3	8	5	3	4
Stratigraphic data (paint stratigraphy, material layers)	9	4	6	7	5	9
Spectroscopic data (FTIR, Raman, XRF, etc.)	12	4	9	6	5	10
Audio and video materials	7	2	6	2	2	4

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING DIFFICULTIES	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats	Legal or institutional restrictions on data sharing	Lack of adequate digital infrastructure for data storage and access	Concerns about intellectual property and data misuse	Limited collaboration among professionals in the field	I have no difficulties in sharing data
Yes, platforms internal to my institution	2	2	4	1	4	1
Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., Trello, Jira, GitHub, Slack)	2	1	1	1	0	0
No, but I'd be interested in using them	6	9	9	8	11	1
No, I don't see their usefulness	1	1	2	0	1	0

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of training or technical expertise	High costs of digital tools or equipment	Difficulty integrating digital data with traditional documentation or methods	Limited institutional support or infrastructure	Resistance to change from colleagues or stakeholders	No significant difficulties
Yes, frequently	2	3	2	3	3	0
Yes, occasionally	8	11	8	7	4	1
No, but I would be interested	3	5	2	4	1	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	2	0	0	0

3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Collaboration between institutions to develop and share interoperable Digital Twin models	Real-time monitoring of conservation conditions	Simulation of environmental factors' impact on material degradation	Virtual planning and testing of restoration interventions	Creation of digital archives for restoration documentation	Support for training and education in conservation	I don't see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	2	3	3	3	2	2	0
Yes, occasionally	8	9	11	10	13	9	0
No, but I would be interested	2	2	3	3	6	6	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of training or technical expertise	High costs of digital tools or equipment	Difficulty integrating digital data with traditional documentation or methods	Limited institutional support or infrastructure	Resistance to change from colleagues or stakeholders	No significant difficulties
Yes, frequently	0	1	1	1	1	0
Yes, occasionally	4	3	4	3	2	0
No, but I would be interested	8	15	6	10	5	1
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	0	3	0	0	0

SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN SUPPORT	Current condition of the object based on the latest data (e.g., imaging, sensors)	Forecast of material deterioration due to environmental factors	Simulations of potential restoration actions and their long-term effects	Alerts and notifications in case of critical changes in the object's condition	Access to historical conservation data and documentation	Tools to compare before/after states or test scenarios
Yes, frequently	1	1	1	1	0	0
Yes, occasionally	6	5	3	4	4	4
No, but I would be interested	11	12	11	13	9	11
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	2	2	0	0	3	1